

Effects of Some Retention Chemicals on Physical Properties of Some Packing Papers

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Abstract

The importance of the packing papers is increasing day by day. Besides, quality and fiber quantity of waste papers are adversely affected. The objective of this study was to improve the properties of some packing papers produced from waste papers by using some commercial retention chemicals (10CE, 40CE, and Eka NP-PL-ATC). Grey cardboards with grammages of 320, 330, 340, and 360 gr/m² were produced by using the retention chemicals in certain rates. Then, the physical properties of the grey cardboards were determined and effects of the retention chemicals on the physical properties of the papers were examined. The results showed that the physical properties of the papers with Eka NP-PL-ATC retention chemical were better than those of the others. The machine and cross direction breaking length and bursting strength of the these grey cardboards were found to be 3066 m, 1544 m, and 4 kg/cm², respectively. Besides, white water was cleaned and contaminants of the discharged water were decreased by adding retention chemicals.

Keywords: Grey cardboard, Packing paper, Retention, Retention aids, Physical properties

Bazı Retansiyon Kimyasallarının Bazı Ambalaj Kağıtlarının Fiziksel Özellikleri Üzerine Etkileri

Özet

Ambalaj kağıtlarının önemi gün geçtikçe artmaktadır. Bunun yanında hammadde olarak kullanılan geri dönüşüm atık kağıt kalitesi ve atık kağıttaki elyaf miktarı düşmektedir. Bu çalışmanın amacı, atık kağıtlardan üretilen bazı ambalaj kağıtlarının fiziksel özelliklerini ticari retansiyon kimyasalları (10CE, 40CE ve Eka NP-PL-ATC) kullanarak iyileştirmektir. Belirli oranlarda retansiyon kimyasalları kullanarak 320, 330, 340, and 360 gr/m² gramajlarında gri karton üretimi yapılmıştır. Elde edilen gri kartonların fiziksel özellikleri belirlenmiş ve retansiyon kimyasallarının bu özellikler üzerine etkisi araştırılmıştır. Elde edilen sonuçlar doğrultusunda Eka NP-PL-ATC retansiyon kimyasalı kullanılarak üretilen gri kartonların fiziksel özelliklerinin diğer kimyasallara göre daha iyi olduğu tespit edilmiştir. Bu gri kartonların boyuna ve enine kopma uzunluğu ile patlama mukavemeti sırasıyla 3066 m, 1544 m, and 4 kg/cm² bulunmuştur. Bununla birlikte retansiyon miktarındaki artışa paralel olarak elek altı suları temizlenmiş, deşarj suyundaki kirlilik azalmıştır.

Anahtar kelimeler: Gri karton, Ambalaj kağıdı, Retansiyon, Retansiyon kimyasalları, Fiziksel özellikler

Introduction

Grey Cardboards (GC) are produced with waste papers such as office papers, old newspapers and magazine papers by fourdrinier paper machine. They are produced with grammages of between 140 gr/m² and 400 gr/m² based on the usage and requirements. Besides, these cardboards can be used in many sectors, such as core tubes, textile products, and separator production. GC is also evaluated as packing papers. Paper and cardboard used as packaging should be subjected to less deformation and included products should be less exposed to external factors during transports. For this reason,

materials used in the production of paper and cardboard should have maximum strength (Casey, 1960). Due to the fact that almost all paper and cardboard are manufactured from recycled paper in Turkey, strength values of the paper and corrugated packaging can be given any desired value. Some searches are being done to increase the strength values; and one of these is retention applications in the fiber suspensions.

Retention is an important issue for paper and cardboard production. Retention of a substance in a system is the ability of the system to retain the substance within the system limits. The efficiency by which components of paper making are retained in a

web of paper as it is being formed. The proportion of a component in a mixture which is found in the mixture in a later process stage (Fellers and Norman, 1998). Retention aids are used to retain filler and fines in the wet paper web during the forming process, by aggregating these stock components to larger units. Hence, retention aids also cause fibers to aggregate, which deteriorate mass formation (Lancaster, 1998).

The components of the paper structure are fibers, fillers, and chemicals. Since the components in the fiber suspension are almost all cationic, anionic chemicals have effects on the retention. There are lots of commercial retention aids for paper production. The objective of this study was to improve the properties of GC produced from waste papers by using some commercial retention chemicals (aids) (10CE, 40CE, and Eka NP-PL-ATC).

Material and Method

Material

GC with grammages of 320, 330, 340, 360 g/m² were manufactured at Kahramanmaraş Paper Mill. Three different retentions chemicals namely 10 CE, 40 CE, and Eka NP-PL-ATC were supplied from Akzo Nobel Chemicals and Archroma Turkey Chemicals.

Pulp preparation and GC production

Mixed office papers (67%) and grey wastes (33%) were used to produce GC. These waste papers were transported to pulper for recycling and pulpified at 4-5% consistency. Then, obtained pulps were beaten to specified freeness levels. The beaten pulps with chemicals and retention aids were subjected to paper machine. The paper machine parameters during the production were presented in Table 1.

According to the results of pretesting (data not shown), the optimum retention dosage was determined to be 400 g/ton. 10CE, 40CE, and Eka NP-PL-ATC retentions chemicals were applied to pulps in this determined dosage.

Table 1. Paper machine parameters during GC production

Grammages ±3	gr/m ²	320	330	340	360
Machine Speed ±10	m/dk	210	195	170	160
Paper Width ±50	mm	2300	2300	2300	2300
Machine Chest					
Cons.	%	4	4	4	4
Machine Chest SR ⁰	%	50	50	50	50
Head Box Cons.					
±0.2	%	1	1	1	1
Wire Pit pH ±0.1	pH	7.2	7.2	7.2	7.2
Wire Pit Conduct.	mS/cm	1300	1300	1300	1300

GC with four different grammages (320, 330, 340, and 360) were produced using fourdrinier paper machine. The Fourdrinier is the most common paper making machine in the world. Fig. 1 shows all of the major sections, but is simplified when compared to most machines in use today.

Figure 1. Fourdrinier paper machine

Papers and boards, being hydrogen-bonded assemblages of cellulose fibers, can be significantly affected by water vapor in the air surrounding the test specimen (Borch et al., 2001). For this reason, all GC were kept in conditioning room at 25 °C and 50% relative humidity for 24 hours accordance with TS 636 EN 20187 (TSE, 1996). Then, physical tests were applied to the GC.

Measurement of retention

Retention gives a practical indication of the efficiency by which fine materials are retained in a web of paper as it is being formed. First-pass retention values can be calculated from two consistency measurements, the headbox consistency, and the white water consistency. There is a very wide diversity of first-pass retention on different paper machines, from less 50% to almost 100%. Retention was calculated by the following equation (Kosonen, 2004);

$$\text{Retention} = [(C_{hb} - C_{ww}) / C_{hb}] * 100\% \quad (1)$$

C_{hb}: headbox consistency,

C_{ww}: white water consistency

Measurement of drainage performance

The drainage performance was evaluated by Schopper-Riegler degree ($^{\circ}$ SR), an important parameter to evaluate the drainage performance of pulp suspensions. When $^{\circ}$ SR is low, the dewatering of the pulp suspension is favorable (Chi et al., 2007). The $^{\circ}$ SR was measured by YT-DJ-100 beating tester, according to ISO 5267-1 (ISO, 1999). The drainage was measured by the amount of the water (ml) passing through sieve of SR tester in five minutes.

Determination of physical properties of GC

All conditioned GC were subjected to physical tests in laboratory. The physical properties of the GC in this study were determined according to the following standards: TS 3121-2 ISO 1924-1 (breaking length machine direction), TS 3121-2 ISO 1924-2 (breaking length cross direction) and TS 3123 EN ISO 2759 (burst strength) (Anon., 1997; Anon., 2004).

Statistical Analysis

The SPSS 15.0 statistical package was used. Data from physical properties of GC analyzed using a computerized statistical program to perform of variance and by carrying out the Duncan test at a $P \leq 0.05$ confidence level.

Results and Discussion

Retention and drainage results

Effects of retention aids on first pass retention during GC production were illustrated in Fig. 2. It can be observed that Eka NP-PL-ATC is more effective than the other retention aids. Besides, it can be clearly seen that there is an interaction between retention and grammage. Athley et al., (2012) reported that an increase in fiber grammage can lead to fewer and smaller pores in the fiber network and thus an increase in the mechanical retention of the particles.

Figure 2. Effects of the retention aids on the retention during GC production with different grammages

According to Fig. 2, Eka NP-PL-ATC gave the best result in retention. The highest retention was found as 92% during GC production with 360 grammages and obtained by using 400 g/ton Eka NP-PL-ATC. When compared retentions for all grammages, Eka NP-PL-ATC was better than other retention aids as seen in Fig. 2.

The drainage (dewatering) of pulp suspension is an important parameter that has a direct influence on the speed of the paper machine and the energy consumption of the drying process (You et al., 2016). Hence, as the evaluating index of drainage performance, the $^{\circ}$ SR was measured (Fig. 3).

Figure 3. Effects of the retention aids on the drainage performance

According to Fig. 3, the drainage time was shortened by using Eka NP-PL-ATC when compared with 10 CE and 40 CE. The drainage performance with using Eka NP-PL-ATC was found as 85 ml/5s. The respective values for 10 CE and 40 CE were 75 and 70 ml/5s, respectively. Paper strength properties show improvement with the shortening of the drainage time (You et al., 2016). As shown in Fig.3, Eka NP-PL-ATC gave the best drainage performance.

Physical properties of GC

The physical properties of the GC produced by using different retention aids were given in Table 2. Pulps obtained from waste papers were beaten to 50 ± 3 °SR freeness level and GC with different grammages (320, 330, 340, 360 g/m²) were produced with the Fourdrinier Paper Machine.

In Table 2, GC produced by using 40 CE with 340 grammages and GC produced by using Eka NP-PL-ATC with 340 and 360 grammages gave the best result in breaking length (MD). When retention aids compared

to each other, Eka NP-PL-ATC gave the highest breaking length (MD). In order to determine statistical effects of retention aids on breaking lengths (MD), the Variance Analysis and Duncan Tests were applied. According to the statistical results, there are significant differences with each other on 5% level of Duncan's test. Roy et al., (2006) and Ordonez et al., (2009) reported that the physical properties of the papers were increased by using retention aids.

Table 2. The physical properties of the GC produced by using different retention aids

Grammages and Retention aids	Breaking Length MD (m)		Breaking Length CD (m)		Burst Strength (kg/cm ²)	
	Mean Value	Standard Deviation	Mean Value	Standard Deviation	Mean Value	Standard Deviation
320 g/m ² 10 CE	2518a	10.13	1238a	20.40	3.27a	0.17
320 g/m ² 40 CE	2568b	6.07	1302b	12.82	3.01a	0.11
320 g/m ² Eka NP-PL-ATC	2648c	6.58	1412c	3.00	2.90b	0.06
330 g/m ² 10 CE	2270a	12.52	1279a	33.18	3.37a	0.10
330 g/m ² 40 CE	2614b	4.91	1318b	17.41	3.19b	0.12
330 g/m ² Eka NP-PL-ATC	2663c	9.02	1470c	2.54	3.00c	0.08
340 g/m ² 10 CE	2059a	6.05	1220a	10.91	3.64a	0.09
340 g/m ² 40 CE	3261b	7.76	1451b	59.46	3.60b	0.08
340 g/m ² Eka NP-PL-ATC	3066c	7.38	1544c	2.71	3.00b	0.13
360 g/m ² 10 CE	2196a	8.69	1084a	27.01	4.00a	0.11
360 g/m ² 40 CE	2681b	10.23	1313b	22.04	3.77b	0.09
360 g/m ² Eka NP-PL-ATC	3106c	11.52	1512c	14.21	2.80c	0.12

*Mean values with the same lower-case letters are not significantly different according to Duncan's mean separation test

GC produced by using Eka NP-PL-ATC with 340 grammages gave the best result in breaking length (CD) as 1544 m. When retention aids compared to each other, Eka NP-PL-ATC gave the highest breaking length (CD) as breaking length (MD). According to the statistical results, there are significant differences with each other on 5% level of Duncan's test.

Eka NP-PL-ATC retention aid gave also the best result in the burst strength. Eka NP-PL-ATC shows an important improvement on burst strength. The highest burst strength was obtained by using this retention aid as 4.00 (kg/cm²). The statistical data showed that there is no significant difference between 10 CE and 40 CE and there are significant differences with Eka NP-PL-ATC for GC with 320 grammages. There is no significant difference between Eka NP-PL-ATC and 40 CE and there are significant differences with

10 CE for GC with 320 grammages. There are significant differences with each other for GC with 330 and 360 grammages.

Conclusion

1. Retention is an important parameter for paper making. It basically affects drainage and paper strength properties. Accordingly, using retention aids has been a need in paper production. The results of this study showed that retention aids have positive effects on retention, drainage, and paper properties. When Eka NP-PL-ATC, 10 CE, and 40 CE retention aids compared with each other, Eka NP-PL-ATC gave the best retention for GC production.

2. The drainage (dewatering) refers to the removal of water from the wet web during the formation of paper and has a direct impact on machine speed. The machine speed affects the amount of production. Therefore, the low

drainage time is desirable for paper-makers and the best drainage performance was obtained by using Eka NP-PL-ATC in this study.

3. Packing papers are generally produced with using waste papers and must have high strength. For this reason, some chemicals are using in paper industry in order to increase strength properties. The retention aids have impact on the drainage which has effects on paper strength. The breaking length and burst strengths are important physical properties for GC. Eka NP-PL-ATC retention aid gave the highest breaking length and burst strength values when compared with other retention aids.

4. The results of this study indicated that using the retention aids in GC production has important roles in terms of paper strength properties and drainage performance. Besides, white water was cleaned and contaminants of the discharged water were decreased by adding retention chemicals.

5. Eka NP-PL-ATC is more suitable retention aids for GC production than 10 CE and 40 CE in terms of retention.

Acknowledgements

This research was supported by the Kahramanmaraş Sutcu Imam University, Research Project Coordination Unit, under project number 2014/1-10 YLS.

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